

COMMUNICATIVE-PRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF ONOMASTICS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: *This article gives information about communicative-pragmatic analysis of noun onomastics of English and Uzbek languages*

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In linguistics, onomastic units have a particular place, as there is no time when humanity and society existed without names. Every language, nation and state owns its onomastic units, proper names. Especially, existing onomastic components in the phraseological layer of the language plays important role in studying nations" historical-cultural heritage. Checking peculiar semantic and national cultural specifications of phraseological units with onomastic components requires the analysis and classification of onomastic component of the phraseological unit. Thus, it makes it important to study comparatively phraseological units with onomastic components in different structural languages. [1]

We will consider some of the features of the speech functioning of English common nouns with the meaning of a person. As the material, words were chosen that act in a speech act in the function of address, i.e. appeals. In this case, it is supposed to determine the pragmatic, and, consequently, the semantic status of the appellatives in terms of their ability to characterize the communicative situation and the communicants themselves. In this regard, the question arises about the relationship between word semantics and linguistic pragmatics.

There are two points of view on this issue: some linguists understand the meaning of a sign as a phenomenon of an exclusively linguistic order, while pragmatics is considered a phenomenon of an extra-linguistic level. The second point of view is characterized by a refusal to understand the meaning of a word as anchoring in a linguistic sign exclusively of what constitutes the narrowest concept of an object.

In the works of recent years, the meaning of the word is understood unusually broadly - as universal and even individual (subjective) knowledge about the subject, as social and personal experience. Within the framework of such an understanding of the meaning, it seems quite reasonable to believe that pragmatics is an aspect of semantics, and the pragmatic aspect of the meaning of a word itself is information about communicants and the conditions for a specific communicative act.

Linguistic pragmatics and semantics are united by the attitude towards understanding the meaning of a word as a process of interpretation: the word is considered as nothing more than a "hint". The task of the researcher is not to decipher it, that is, to recode, but to establish what lies behind it.

A similar approach to the pragmatics of the word received coverage in the works of sociolinguists.

Currently, few people dispute the pragmatic fullness of the linguistic sign. However, the recognition of this fact inevitably leads to the conclusion about the fallacy of the opinion expressed by some linguists about the semantic inferiority of appellatives, since the presupposition part of the lexical meaning highlighted by modern semantics is an object that is unusually heterogeneous in its composition and the nature of the information it contains: it can be information about the situation, social status of communicants, nationally determined connotations, etc.

The greatest coverage in linguistic literature and especially in practical manuals received the English forms of polite address or speech clichés Mr., lady, sir and others, which are sometimes cited as an example of semantic emptiness. However, the very fact that there are numerous recommendations as to who, to whom, under what conditions can apply, using this or that form, shows their pragmatic significance, in other words, their "social orientation".

So, for the appellatives madam and sir, it usually consists in indicating that P_x occupies a socially lower or situationally more dependent position in relation to the addressee of the speech; P_x tries to demonstrate explicit or outward reverence for P_r . There are also fairly standard situations in which the appellants madam and sir signal the status of the communicants. For example, the following composition is quite likely for sir: P_x is a student, and P_U is a teacher. English intraschool etiquette does not provide for any other way of addressing a teacher and a man. The pragmatic meaning of the word madam can be revealed in a similar remark: Excuse me, madam, would you mind if I open the window?

The use of onomastics, first of all – precedent names, pragmatically significant place names and anthroponyms - is among the means that contribute to the strengthening of the figurativeness and expressiveness of the statement and the text as a whole.

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